

Project Title **Implementing FAIR Workflows: a proof of concept study in the field of consciousness**

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D1.2 Mid-term Project Report

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Authors **Xiaoli Chen** <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0207-2705>
Helena Cousijn <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6660-6214>
Zefan Zheng <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9631-7560>
Shawn Ross <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6492-9025>
Martin Jagerhorn <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5442-5838>
Martin O'Connor <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2256-2421>
Maria Praetzellis <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5047-3090>
Brian Riley <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9870-5882>

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Executive summary

The Implementing FAIR Workflows project is a 3 year project to implement exemplar workflows in cognitive neuroscience research, based on existing persistent identifier (PID) and metadata infrastructure. In the project, a research team at the Max Planck Institute for Empirical Aesthetics (MPIEA) works closely with scholarly infrastructure experts at DataCite through the entirety of a two-part study to examine each step of the research process, and put FAIR recommendations into practice. The project is supported by five partner organizations that provide research supporting services through the implementation of PID and metadata features, to improve interoperability between platforms and simplify the workflows for the researchers.

In this document, we provide a review of the work and the achievements of the first 18 months of the project, presenting a brief summary of quarterly outputs and a list of engagement events. Also featured are perspectives from the project director, the project partners, and the researchers that are leading the studies. Through a series of structured interviews, they share their experiences working in and contributing to the project, and evaluation of the progress so far.

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Project mid-term review

Year 1, Q1 (September 2021 - November 2021): During the initial three months of the project, we successfully onboarded the project team and aligned project goals across the partners. We established an advisory committee consisting of experts in both neuroscience and Open Science domains. In addition, we created the project branding materials and an online webpage¹. With the initial engagement with the community through various channels, we generated interest and volunteer participation in the testing and dissemination of project outputs.

Year 1, Q2 (December 2021 - February 2022): The following quarter, along with the continuation of the workflow specification development, the project efforts were focused on establishing alignment with the development roadmaps of the partners with the project activities, developing the project communication plan (Chen, 2022) and submitting proposals to various conferences and workshops. The researchers used OSF and published two preregistrations for pilot experiments (Zheng et al., 2022; Zheng & Trubutschek, 2022).

Year 1, Q3 (March 2022 - May 2022): We defined a schedule of work for partner contributions in the third quarter. Project partners committed to implementing a number of integrations that will support the incorporation of persistent identifiers into research workflows and create entry points for metadata enrichment. We also carried out two workshops to kick-off the dashboard product design process. The research group published the data management plan (Zheng, 2022) using the DMPTool platform.

Year 1, Q4 (June 2022 - August 2022): In the fourth quarter, we delivered the project dissemination plan (Chen et al., 2022), outlining the various ways we will be engaging with different stakeholders to convey the message and the lessons learned from the project experience. The research team started the process of developing a method for domain-specific metadata template building and engaged with the INCF community for feedback. The researchers published another preregistration (Zheng, 2022) for the main experiment for the first study.

In the first year of the project, the project team has established a mutual understanding of the project goals and objectives with the project partners, as reflected in the statements of work and signed agreements with the project partners. We put in place a collaboration and communication structure, and defined concrete action plans to meet all deliverables. We raised the visibility of the project by engaging with different communities, including building formal relations with the community through the project advisory committee and other FAIR projects. Finally, we have outlined

¹ <https://datacite.org/fair-workflows.html>

components of the dissemination work, to ensure the project outputs will prove to be meaningful, useful, and sustainable even after the project lifetime.

Box 1. Excerpt from year 1 progress report.

Year 2, Q1 (September 2022 - November 2022): In fall 2022, we delivered the workflow specification document. The document outlined the workflow we are following, and how this can be used by integrators and researchers. For integrators, we explain how the different project partners contribute to enhanced interoperability between systems to enable FAIR workflows, For researchers, we provide a step-by-step workflow explaining at which stage which outputs should be deposited, which PIDs can then be registered, and which metadata is needed to make the outputs—and the connections between outputs—available to the community.

Year 2, Q2 (December 2022 - February 2023): We have focused on building and testing the domain-specific metadata template. The project team has organized an in-person template workshop to work on metadata property selection, prioritization, and definition, resulted in a draft template that underwent three rounds of testing and iteration. The full report on the metadata template for human cognitive neuroscience research is submitted together with the template itself as the project deliverable 2.2.

Engagement activities

The table below provides an overview of the main activities the project engaged in the first half of the project period, including project wide workshops, intra-project cross-pollination workshops, and public facing conference appearances. We presented the project at five international conferences, organized four workshops with participants from different stakeholder groups, and presented in three webinars to engage the wider data management and persistent identifier communities.

Date	Title	Type
Past		
2021.10	All-hands kick-off	workshop
2021.11	DataCite Open Hours	webinar
2022.5	EuroCris 2022	conference
2022.6	17th International Digital Curation Conference	conference
2022.7	RDA Plenary 2022	conference

2022.9	INCF Assembly	conference
2022.9	Better Together	webinar
2022.9	CZI Open Science Meeting	conference
2022.10	FAIR-IMPACT T3.2 Kick-off	workshop
2022.11	DataCite Open Hours	webinar
2022.11	Paper-Data Linking Workshop series	workshop
2022.12	Project team workshop	workshop
Planned		
2023.3	RDA Plenary 2023	conference
2023.4	FORCE2023	conference
2023.5	RDA Decade of Data	webinar
2023.9	EOSC symposium	conference
2023.10	International Data Week	conference
2023.10	Project all-hands	workshop

Table 1. Engagement activities.

We have already planned for a number of important events for 2023, including the first in-person project all-hands meeting co-located with the International Data Week conference, where we will also submit a session.

Project Director's mid-term retrospective

In this section, Helena Cousijn (Community Engagement Director, DataCite), the project director of the FAIR Workflows projects, shares her thoughts on the work so far.

What was the original idea and goal behind the project?

From my perspective, the project started with three different goals in mind: 1) show how existing systems can integrate (more) to enable FAIR workflows; 2) demonstrate together with a research

group what FAIR looks like in practice; and 3) provide a workflow that can be used by funders to enable FAIRer research outputs.

Have the ideas and goals of the project shifted over time?

All three goals are still important, but I think following the reviews of the grant proposal and community feedback during the project that the emphasis is most strongly on goal 2. There is a lot of interest in the community in seeing what it means for researchers to do FAIR research from start to finish.

What have been the biggest accomplishments of the project to date?

I am personally really pleased with deliverable 1.1 which outlines the workflow in detail. This provides a strong basis for a researcher guide and a funder guide.

What do you see as the biggest challenges coming up in the next phase?

I think one of the biggest challenges is tracking how much time researchers actually spend on FAIR workflows, because many steps are intertwined with other research practices.

How has the community responded to the undertakings of the project?

People really like the idea of testing out workflows with researchers as part of their research practices. Many people working in this field recognize that there can be a gap between the work done by the open science/RDM community and the day- to-day work of researchers, so they appreciate our efforts to bring these things together.

What are some takeaways from the experience engaging in FAIR practices so far?

There are many questions about the why, which is an indication that the incentives need to be clearer.

Anything else you would like to emphasize about making research FAIR?

The infrastructure is available and it doesn't have to be complicated. Small steps such as depositing different outputs into repositories can make a big difference.

Researcher's mid-term retrospective

In this section, Zefan Zheng, the researcher carrying out his project with FAIR practices implemented throughout his PhD research, shares his perspective and experience in the process.

Figure 1. From the traditional research workflow to FAIR workflow in practice.

Traditionally, only publishing the paper that describes a deliberately selected portion of experiments conducted is considered in a research workflow (see Figure 1). Such scientific practice hinders the reproducibility and reusability of research outcomes. This is like only offering a cherry without the cake that makes the cherry valuable in the first place.

Therefore, we proposed that a FAIR research workflow shall include opening and describing all significant research outputs that support the reproducibility and reusability, such as pre-registration, data, code, protocol, preprint, and potentially registered reports.

However, when putting the proposed workflow into practice, it came to our attention that we were still not telling the full story as a lot of valuable data was produced during the piloting phase of a research life cycle. These data, often showing null results, fell rarely within the scope of any open science practice, despite the rising awareness that null results are scientifically equally valuable. Driven by such motivations, we have attempted to preregister all pilot experiments, publicly share the code and data produced in these experiments, and open the brief report that describes the experiments, code, and data.

In this way, the FAIR workflow in practice (Figure 1) not only shows the main experiment that can lead to a significant scientific breakthrough, but also exhibits the long but informative journey before the breakthrough. Other researchers will, therefore, not have to repeat the hard but normally hidden journey when they want to pick up similar paradigms.

Despite so many well-known advantages, practicing open science for most researchers still feels too time-consuming and benefits mainly the field, i.e., others, rather than the researchers themselves. Here, we argue that this is not and will most likely not be the case for our research workflow. Our following arguments will address the two main concerns mentioned above, respectively.

1. FAIR practices are too time consuming. Time consuming is one of the most popular excuses that researchers use to refuse implementing open science practice. However, we find little empirical evidence for this argument. We have been tracking the time costs of every practice that is included in the FAIR workflow in practice but not in the traditional research workflow over the past months. We found that these “extra” practices cost around 10% of the overall working hours of the PhD student who is in charge of the experiments. One way to save time is to re-adopt the upstream outputs in the downstream outputs. For example, the main text of pre-registration could be used when drafting the brief reports, protocols, and papers. Coding the analysis in RMarkdown in R language or JupiterNotebook in Python could make a well-commented code easily into a brief report.

Figure 2. From one citable research output to many.

2. Little benefits for open science practitioners. Academia credits scientists mainly based on the number of research outputs (normally only papers) and citations these research outputs attract over the years. The only citable research outputs in the traditional research workflow are articles. However, our project is dedicated to also publishing and more importantly registering DOIs for preregistrations, protocols, brief reports, code, and data, which makes the citable, i.e., credible, research outputs from one to five or more in one research project as shown in Figure 2.

D1.2 Mid-term Project report

The research team is approaching the end of Project 1 out of two proposed research projects in the span of three years while following the FAIR workflow in practice. Four preregistrations, four datasets, and four pieces of analysis code, and four brief reports are available for publicly sharing so far. We are now working on the research outputs for the main experiment of Project 1. Piloting for Project 2 will follow soon. All research outputs produced in Project 1 will be publicly shared after the final paper of Project 1 is accepted at a Preprint server.

Project partners on integration implementation

In this section, project partners that are developing and implementing integrations based on PID and metadata workflows share their thoughts on their work so far.

The responsible people of each partner organization were invited to briefly introduce their platform or service and the integrations they are building in the project, followed by where they are in the process, the challenges encountered so far, and any recommendations for future integrators.

Australian Research Data Commons

Shawn Ross, RAiD product manager

Natasha Simmons, Associate Director, Data & Services

Could you briefly introduce your platform/service, and how do the FAIR principles fit into the vision?

A Research Activity Identifier (RAiD) is a globally unique, persistent identifier (PID) for research projects or activities. It consists of a unique identifier (a handle) and a metadata record. The metadata record links various components (e.g., contributors, organisations, grants, instruments, publications, datasets, etc.) to the project, via their own PIDs where available (e.g., ORCiDs, RORs, Crossref Grant IDs, DOIs, etc.). These components are only linked to the project itself; a RAiD does not assert links between components (e.g., contributors to organisations). RAiDs also contain project information not found elsewhere, such as project title, start date, description, and subject, but does not duplicate information found elsewhere. RAiDs can also be linked to one another using arbitrary qualified relationships so that, e.g., subprojects can be created.

RAiD supports the FAIR Principles by providing an international identification system for research projects as well as comprehensive information about research projects (loosely defined). Such information, including both linked PIDs and key project information found nowhere else, provide important metadata for related datasets. Transparency and understanding are further promoted by the fact that RAiDs capture a history of all changes to a project, so the state of a project (such as contributors and their roles) at any given time can be retrieved (and matched with datasets produced at that time). Since most research happens in the context of a project of one sort or another, this addition to the PID ecosystem is likely to have significant impact. Finally, the utilisation of other PIDs parallels PID use in FAIR data; if an existing PID holds needed information, it is referenced instead of copying that information. Existing data is thus linked wherever possible; only project information that cannot be found anywhere else is newly created in a RAiD.

What are the integrations your system is implementing in the project?

We plan to integrate with the other research PIDs, including:

- DataCite DOIs (including IGSNs)
- Crossref DOIs
- ORCID
- ROR
- Instrument PIDs (forthcoming)

We will also integrate with other services that can uniquely identify project metadata, such as GeoNames for project spatial coverage.

The RAiD system will offer a modern API to facilitate integration with local systems as well. A single, global endpoint for discovering, resolving, and retrieving metadata from RAiDs will be provided.

Can you describe the process of developing your integration and any challenges you encountered?

We are in the early stages of integration development. We expect integration of other PIDs to proceed from (1) unvalidated text fields for related PIDs, to (2) text fields where the format of the PID is validated, to (3) validation of the PID with the originating service, to (4) validation of the PID with the originating service, including preview of the information it contains so that users are certain they have the correct PID.

We may eventually cache some information from the PID (e.g., contributor names), but we do not duplicate any such information into RAiD metadata, only the PID itself (plus some administrative metadata) is stored.

Which step in the process are you currently at and what are the next steps?

We are still implementing (1) above, and will proceed through the others to (4) as rapidly as possible.

How do you envision the implementation will make an impact? In what way can the impact be measured?

The three major impacts we see from RAiD are:

1. Elimination of double-entry of data by providing all contributors and organisations with a 'single source of truth' for a project when, for example, they apply for grants or produce reports. An Australian cost-benefit analysis produced by The MoreBrains Cooperative indicates that widely implementing three PIDs, including RAiD, could save as much as 38,000 person-days, or \$24M in direct costs, per year (Brown, Josh et al., 2022).
2. RAiDs will support more thorough reporting. They provide longer-term and broader reporting than (for example) grant IDs, noting that some project outputs are not produced

until long after any particular grant has been closed. They also act as a nexus bringing together various project personnel, inputs, and outputs, facilitating production of research graphs (arguably in a more reliable manner than those deduced from existing PIDs).

3. FAIR data facilitation via comprehensive project metadata. Domain-specific metadata standards often require project-level metadata, as it is useful in understanding datasets produced by a project. RAiDs provide not only a current snapshot of project metadata, but maintain a history of it as well.

Any advice for other platforms or tools that are considering PID-related integrations?

PID services are difficult and expensive to build - don't build new ones unless the case is compelling. It took some time, for instance, to reason through why grant IDs cannot substitute [for project IDs].

How can the project team support your work in the future?

Through regular updates on overall project progress, sharing challenges and lessons learned that might be applicable to RAiD.

In person meeting between the project team and the RAiD team scheduled for March 2023.

ChronosHub

Martin Jagerhorn, Head of business development

Could you briefly introduce your platform/service, and how do the FAIR principles fit into the vision?

ChronosHub is the world's leading Open Access management platform and serves to manage all types of Open Access. Workflow automation is the essence of what we're doing, and especially to ensure an outstanding user experience for the researchers. In order to achieve automation, we need to integrate the ChronosHub platform with all kinds of systems across the ecosystem, and currently have 100+ connections with systems for submission & peer-review, finance, production, payments, institutional repositories, research management systems, authentication, and online publication databases. The most important pre-requisite for a seamless integration is that ChronosHub, but also these other systems, apply the FAIR principles as far as possible. First of all, the systems need to offer an API to technically enable a machine-to-machine exchange. Secondly, Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) for all the relevant entities that are being exchanged between the ChronosHub platform and these other systems is a must, as anything else requires manual validation.

What are the integrations your system is implementing in the project?

Through the FAIR Workflows project, we are extending ChronosHub to also support research datasets and Data Management Plans (DMPs). For these entities we are adding integrations between ChronosHub and DataCite as well as with Dryad. This means that the authors easily can associate datasets and DMPs with their research articles and other grant outputs in ChronosHub. Through the integration with DataCite, authors will be able to get already deposited datasets and DMPs listed as suggestions for their articles, both at manuscript submission and article acceptance. Through the integration with Dryad, the authors will be able to deposit datasets via ChronosHub, also both at manuscript submission and article acceptance.

Can you describe the process of developing your integration and any challenges you encountered?

The initial work included joint meetings and workshops between the different partners in the FAIR Workflows project in order to define the scope. The partners have subsequently provided the necessary API documentation, which has been reviewed to specify the integrations and other needed development work to extend the support in ChronosHub to datasets and DMPs. We are right now in the implementation process, which will be followed by testing and quality assurance.

We originally planned to integrate with Dryad via CEDAR, which provides dynamic templates for domain specific ontologies to categorize the datasets. However, the challenge encountered was that CEDAR and Dryad were not already integrated with each other in such a way that integration via CEDAR was possible. It was therefore jointly decided in the project to do the integration directly between ChronosHub and Dryad instead.

Which step in the process are you currently at and what are the next steps?

We are currently in the implementation process of integrating ChronosHub with DataCite and Dryad, and extending the capabilities on the ChronosHub platform to support datasets and DMPs in an easy way. The next step is testing and quality assurance.

How do you envision the implementation will make an impact? In what way can the impact be measured?

ChronosHub supports FAIR workflows for many institutions, funders and publishers worldwide, and the extension to support datasets and DMPs will be beneficial to all these stakeholders, in particular to unburden the researchers from the administrative work along the author journey. It will also facilitate for authors to be compliant with funder and institutional policies.

The impact can be measured in degree of policy compliance for the funders and institutions on the ChronosHub platform. It can also be measured in terms of ease of use / appreciation by the

researchers. This could for example be done by measuring the Net Promoter Score (NPS) of this specific service of facilitating for authors to manage their datasets and DMPs.

Any advice for other platforms or tools that are considering PID-related integrations?

Only the obvious: ensure that your own platform supports the most relevant PIDs for all entities involved in the integration. Typically, this should include ORCID for the researchers, ROR and Ringgold for the organisations, DataCite DOIs for datasets and DMPs, CrossRef DOIs for articles and grants, ISSNs for the journals, ROR and Ringgold IDs for publishers, and ROR, Ringgold and Funder Registry IDs for funders.

How can the project team support your work in the future?

Overall, the support works fine currently, with regular check-ins for mutual updates. Joint project meetings were held a bit more in the beginning, and it could be good to have a few more such meetings, e.g. quarterly, going forward. Shorter, project-wide updates e.g. per email or via Slack, would also be good.

CEDAR

Martin O'Connor, Technical lead

Could you briefly introduce your platform/service, and how do the FAIR principles fit into the vision?

The Center for Expanded Data Annotation and Retrieval (CEDAR) was established in 2014 to create a computational ecosystem for development, evaluation, use, and refinement of biomedical metadata.

Our approach centers on the use of metadata templates, which define the data elements needed to describe particular types of biomedical experiments. The templates include controlled terms and synonyms for specific data elements. CEDAR uses a library of such templates to help scientists submit annotated datasets to appropriate online data repositories.

CEDAR adopts metadata templates as a fundamental mechanism by which groups of investigators can capture and communicate their requirements for the metadata needed to make their datasets FAIR.

It provides an array of mechanisms to support the creation of FAIR metadata using these templates. These tools include (1) the CEDAR Workbench, which supports the creation, deployment, management, and publication of metadata templates, and (2) the FAIRware Workbench, which uses metadata templates to assess the degree to which existing online data resources actually are FAIR.

What are the integrations your system is implementing in the project?

CEDAR metadata templates are digital objects that can be used to describe metadata about scientific experiments. We are in the processing of using DataCite services to generate DOIs for these digital objects.

The goal is to provide functionality to allow CEDAR users to interactively generate DOIs for metadata templates that they wish to publish. The system will prompt users to provide a detailed description of these templates; it will then use these descriptions to request DOIs from the DataCite system and store those DOIs in the metadata templates.

Can you describe the process of developing your integration and any challenges you encountered?

The integrations process has the following main steps: (1) work with DataCite to determine the requirements for generating DOIs using its APIs, (2) extend CEDAR's metadata template specification to support the representation of DOIs, (3) provide front and back end capabilities in the CEDAR system to allow users to request the generation of DOIs for their metadata templates, and (4) invoke DataCite APIs to generate DOIs for CEDAR metadata templates.

Which step in the process are you currently at and what are the next steps?

We have finalized the requirements for generating DOIs for CEDAR templates using the DataCite system. We are currently extending CEDAR's metadata template specification to support DOIs as a first-class model component and are also developing software to allow users to interactively request the generation of these DOIs. The next step requires the development of software to invoke DataCite DOI-generation APIs.

How do you envision the implementation will make an impact? In what way can the impact be measured?

We hope that the ability to generate DOIs for CEDAR metadata templates will both (1) increase the use of CEDAR for generating FAIR metadata specifications since users will now be able to publish to specifications, and (2) will allow researchers to find existing published metadata templates using the discovery capabilities provided by DataCite-based search.

The impact can be measured by the monitoring of the number of DOIs created for CEDAR metadata templates and by the number of templates discovered by DataCite-based searches.

How can the project team support your work in the future?

The project team is providing great support. No improvements needed.

Dryad

Maria Praetzellis, Dryad Product Manager
(temporary)

Could you briefly introduce your platform/service, and how do the FAIR principles fit into the vision?

Dryad is a curated general-purpose repository that makes the data underlying scientific publications discoverable, freely reusable, and citable. Any journal or publisher that wishes to encourage data archiving may refer authors to Dryad. Dryad welcomes data submissions related to any published or accepted peer-reviewed scientific and medical literature, particularly data for which no specialized repository exists.

What are the integrations your system is implementing in the project?

This project is building on the ability of the CEDAR technology to acquire and encode standardized metadata for different scientific communities, using established reporting guidelines for different classes of experiments and standard terms for authoring metadata.

Can you describe the process of developing your integration and any challenges you encountered?

The Dryad piece of this integration involves integrating the CEDAR Embeddable Editor that displays within the Dryad interface and populating this embeddable editor with CEDAR-supplied metadata fields.

Data description

Standardized metadata

Fill out a standardized metadata form for your discipline to make your data more useful to others.

Choose a metadata form

Templeton Draft for Neuroscience Data

Keywords: Adding keywords improves the findability of your dataset. E.g. scientific names, method type

Methods: How was this dataset collected? How has it been processed?

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Figure 1: Image of the Data Submission form where a user can select the metadata template

Figure 2: Image of the metadata template for Human Cognitive Neuroscience Data

How do you envision the implementation will make an impact? In what way can the impact be measured?

Dryad developers have incorporated the CEDAR editor within the Dryad interface. This is currently available for testing in the Dryad stage environment. The next phase of work involves testing the template with researchers. If modifications to the metadata fields or layout of the editor are needed, this will come from the CEDAR team, and the Dryad developers will load the updated template. Additionally, there were some accessibility issues identified with the CEDAR Embeddable Editor that will need to be addressed by the CEDAR team before Dryad can deploy the editor to the production environment.

The only additional work required from the Dryad team is to finalize the autosave process and test the saving workflow with users.

Any advice for other platforms or tools that are considering PID-related integrations?

The biggest issue that the Dryad team has experienced in our various PID integrations is challenges around the stability and availability of PID services. There have been some instances where having

a local copy of a PID registry can be helpful to ensure consistent uptime of the service. As newer PIDs mature and their services become more reliable, we expect that relying on API-based integrations will be more reliable.

How can the project team better support your work in the future?

Dryad would be interested in getting feedback from the research team on utilizing the CEDAR editor and how this new step in data deposit fits within their workflow.

California Digital Library (DMPTool)

Maria Praetzellis, DMPTool Product Manager

Brian Riley, DMPTool Technical Lead

Could you briefly introduce your platform/service, and how do the FAIR principles fit into the vision?

The DMPTool was developed from a grassroots effort of eight institutions beginning in January 2011. These institutions came together in direct response to demands from funding agencies, such as the National Science Foundation (NSF), that researchers plan to manage their research data. The DMPTool was developed in an effort to consolidate expertise and reduce costs in addressing data management needs at their respective institutions. This original mission still serves as the guiding principle of the DMPTool as the application continues to be free and community-supported.

Recent feature developments have focused on transforming the DMP from a static text file into an interoperable, networked hub of information wherein details about a research project can be updated and queried over the project's lifetime. This new Networked DMP allows information within a DMP to be fed across stakeholders, linking metadata, repositories, and institutions, and allowing for notifications and verification, reporting in real-time. A key goal of this new system is to reduce the burden on researchers by generating automated updates to a plan and facilitating seamless integration with systems and groups that support research.

What are the integrations your system is implementing in the project?

To support the work of the Templeton World Charity Foundation-funded FAIR Workflows project, the DMP Tool team will partner with Paula Reeves Consulting on the related work outlined in the attached document. The focus of our combined efforts is to build a PID-enabled FAIR workflow that tracks research from planning to publication.

Specifically, the work described intentionally highlights and builds on the deliverables and goals of the FAIR Workflows work packages.

1. **DMPTool Administrator Dashboard:** The planned, new Administrator Dashboard will offer a quick overview of DMPs with DMP-IDs and the ability to view the current project status and any associated project outputs, including data repositories utilized. In addition, the dashboard will include reporting and tracking features designed for institutions seeking to document compliance with data-sharing mandates. The DMPTool Product Manager will coordinate user testing to iterate on what information is displayed on this dashboard and what features are required to optimize the utility of the dashboards for administrators.
2. **Upload of DMPs & creation of DMP-IDs:** This planned, new feature will ingest PDF versions of DMPs and expose this information in a machine-readable format, including the ability to connect DMPs to associated research outputs. This is needed because most DMPs are not created with the DMPTool; however, there is still a need to structure these DMPs to generate DMP-IDs. For example, the MPIEA team had a previously written DMP for their research, which we will be able to build off of with this new workflow. With this new feature, users will upload a PDF of an existing DMP and enter basic metadata about the project. Connections to funder APIs will automatically transfer relevant metadata to avoid duplication of data entry. Uploaded DMPs will get a DMP ID. With these DMP-IDs, researchers and administrators can connect outputs related to their project, ultimately allowing for notifications and compliance reporting.
3. **API Integrations:** The new system will facilitate updating information associated with DMP-IDs via API-based integrations with external funder and research systems. For example, we are working with the NSF and NIH awards APIs to harvest funding and project information for inclusion in the DMP. We are also exploring integrations with the [OpenAIRE Research Graph](#) and [DataCite Commons](#), which have robust APIs providing metadata and links between research outputs, organizations, funders, and datasets.

DMPTool - Create/Upload DMP Workflow

The new DMPTool upload form will be used to capture high level information about the DMP and upload the DMP.

Note: the example form here only shows a sample of the information that will be collected.

DMPTool - DMP augmentation workflow

Note: This is an example of a DMP ID landing page. Text in green represents hyperlinks to external systems (e.g. ROR, ORCID, other DOIs, etc.)

Can you describe the process of developing your integration and any challenges you encountered?

Thus far, our development work has centered around building the backend infrastructure required to build these integrations. The DMPTool is a very small team of one developer and one product manager, so our principal challenge is a lack of resources to meet the development goals of our

work. The Templeton project has come forward to help with this gap, and additional funding will allow for additional development resources to help us progress to the next phase of work faster.

Which step in the process are you currently at, and what are the next steps?

We have built the back-end infrastructure and will begin working on the front-end UX work starting in March.

How do you envision the implementation will make an impact? In what way can the impact be measured?

By integrating the DMP into the PID (and associated metadata) ecosystem and using APIs to connect to repositories, libraries will be better equipped to track and manage their institutional research data products, and institutional data services will be better positioned to communicate and collaborate.

Any advice for other platforms or tools that are considering PID-related integrations?

When working with PIDs maintained by an external system:

- Verify the system's retention and access policies (will a PID always be resolvable), if not how will your application handle that?
- Make sure that the PIDs are either URLs or at least have a namespace so that you can ensure uniqueness (e.g. an external system may use the id HEWG94HG49G4G which is unique for that system but not globally unique)
- Make sure you understand how they manage versioning. Some systems have different PIDs for each version while others always return the latest version of the object

When working with PIDs your application maintains:

- Make sure you clearly document your retention and access policies (e.g. are they publicly available 24x7, can the objects they resolve to be embargoed or restricted, etc.)
- Make sure your PIDs are resolvable in the browser
- Make sure you support versioning and then clearly document how that works
- Consider using a system like Crossref or DataCite to register your PIDs so that they become part of the larger DOI ecosystem

How can the project team better support your work in the future?

I'd be interested in getting feedback from the research team on utilizing the new workflows that we're developing.

D1.2 Mid-term Project report

Summary

The services provided by the project partners touch on different stages of the research lifecycle, while the partners are working on a diverse set of development goals and priorities, they are all on-track with the work towards the development milestones. The organizations identified two main impacts these integrations will have: alleviating workload for both the researchers and research administration, and increasing FAIRness of outputs.

Next Steps

March 2023 marks the beginning of the second half of the project. The project team will focus on the development of the funder and researcher guides, as well as the project centric dashboard, seeking dissemination partners for these outputs, and continuing to work with the project partners to support the system integration and documentation efforts.

Specifically, The project is liaising with the Open Research Funders Group and other PID organizations to formulate a guiding document for using PID-centric workflows to enable output tracking, a work that will be unfolding in the following months. The technical specification of the FAIR dashboard will be drawn in the following quarter, which will cater to some key use cases and complement the guides by demonstrating evidence for connections and impact of research project.

The project team is also actively involved in the Research Data Alliance via the Working with PIDs in Tools Interest Group, a newly established forum where use cases of research platform interoperability are shared and challenges in design, develop, and implementation discussed. In terms of dissemination, the project team is looking to participate in several researcher facing FAIR practice communities of interest such as ReproducibiliTEA² (Frankford group) and the Edinburgh Open Research Conference 2023³, and planning to contribute to existing Open practice guides such as The Turing Way⁴.

² <https://reproducibilitea.org/>

³ <http://journals.ed.ac.uk/eor>

⁴ <https://the-turing-way.netlify.app/welcome.html>

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